

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids : Solvent Extraction of Metal Ions with N-p-chlorophenyl-2-theno-hydroxamic Acid

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The solvent extraction of several metal ions with N-p-chlorophenyl-2-theno-hydroxamic acid is investigated qualitatively. The coloured chloroform extractable complexes of Ce(IV), Cu(II), Fe(II, III), Ti(IV), U(VI), V(V) and Zr(IV) are attractively suited for further examination for colorimetric determination and solvent separation.

N-PHENYLBENZOHYDROXAMIC acid¹⁻⁶ and its analogues^{7,8} are now widely used for solvent separation and colorimetric determination of metal ions. In the present communication the solvent extraction studies with N-p-chlorophenyl-2-theno-hydroxamic acid, trivial name CPTHA⁹, with metal ions are briefly described.

CPTHA

The distribution constant of this new compound between chloroform and water is 215 ± 5 at 25°. Its solutions in chloroform and alcohol are very stable. The chloroform extracts with metal ions too have excellent storage stability. Extraction of metal ions is generally rapid but is dependent on the acidity of the aqueous phase. In figures 1 and 2 the typical spectra of the coloured extracts in near UV and visible regions are presented. The spectral characteristics of these extracts and conditions of reactions are given in Table 1. It is observed that

TABLE-1 SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COLOURED CPTHA METAL ION EXTRACTS IN CHLOROFORM

Metal Ion	Aqueous Phase, pH	Colour of Extract	Wavelength of absorption maximum, nm
Ce ⁴⁺	8N HCl	Yellow	GA
Ce ⁴⁺	1-2	Yellow	365
Cu ²⁺	1-2	Yellow	GA
Fe ²⁺	2-4	Red	445
Fe ³⁺	2-4	Red	445
Ti ⁴⁺	8N HCl	Yellow	348
UO ₂ ²⁺	2-4	Yellow	GA
VO ₂ ⁺	2-10N HCl	Violet	530
VO ₃ ⁺	0-1 N HCl	Brown	465
Zr ⁴⁺	2-3	Yellow	375

GA=General Absorption.

FIG. 1 Absorption spectra of CPTHA extracts in chloroform

FIG.2 ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF CPTHA EXTRACTS IN CHLOROFORM

CPTHA is a versatile extractive reagent. Of the many metal ions which give coloured extracts with CPTHA in chloroform Ce(IV), Fe(II, III), Ti(IV), V(V) and Zr(IV) only show well defined absorption band. Cu(II) and UO₂²⁺ exhibit general absorption. Ce(IV) gives yellow extracts both from weakly and strongly acidic solutions but the stoichiometric composition of complexes seem to be different. For example, its yellow extract at pH 2 gives a broad band at 365 nm whereas the extract obtained from 8N hydrochloric acid shows general absorption only. A number of common metal ions such as Al(III), Mn(II),

Pb(II) and others gave colourless extracts. Rare earth ions gave both coloured and colourless extracts but their extraction was very sensitive to pH of the aqueous phase; these were partially extracted even on long periods of shaking with concentrated solutions of CPTHA. The coloured extracts are attractively suited for detailed investigation for colorimetric applications. These and their extraction parameters in various other water-immiscible solvents are being further investigated. The colourless extracts are not likely to be useful for direct quantitative determination of metal ions although these may find applications in solvent separations.

Experimental

Apparatus :

The spectra of coloured metal hydroxamates were recorded on SPECORD, Carl Zeiss, Jena ultraviolet-visible recording spectrophotometer equipped with matched quartz cells of 10 mm path length. Narrow range and wide range indicator papers were used for rapid and approximate measurement of pH. Accurate measurement of pH was made on Systronics pH meter.

Solutions of Diverse Ions :

The solutions of various ions were prepared from A.R. grade salts following the procedure of West¹⁰. The concentration of the desired ion was generally 20 mg. per ml.

Reagent Solution :

A 0.1% solution of CPTHA in ethyl alcohol free chloroform was used for all extraction work.

Buffer Solutions :

10% w/v. aqueous solutions of sodium and ammonium acetates and ammonium chloride were used as buffer.

General Procedure for Solvent Extraction of CPTHA with Metal Ions :

In a short-stemmed pear shaped separatory funnel 5 to 10 ml solution, containing 2 to 5 mg of the metal ion to be tested, was taken and the acidity was adjusted to a desired value by the addition of acid, alkali or buffer solution. The solution was shaken vigorously with 5 to 10 ml of the reagent solution in chloroform for about 5 minutes or longer. The organic layer was then separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and tested, whenever necessary, for extraction of metal ion by suitable spot tests. The absorption spectra of coloured metal extracts were recorded after suitable dilution.

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